

Breast MRI in the Prone Position: Impact on RF-induced Heating of Active Implantable Medical Devices

Supplementary Data

This file contains supplementary figures (S1–S4).

1. Figure S1. Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, Extracochlear and Intracochlear implants at 1.5 T MRI (64 MHz).
2. Figure S2. Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, Extracochlear and Intracochlear implants at 3.0 T MRI (128 MHz).
3. Figure S3. Comparison of Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, extracochlear and intracochlear implants between direct non-huygens simulation and huygens simulation at 1.5T MRI (64MHz).
4. Figure S4. Comparison of Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, extracochlear and intracochlear implants between direct non-huygens simulation and huygens simulation at 3.0T MRI (128MHz).

Figure S1. Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, Extracochlear and Intracochlear implants at 1.5 T MRI (64 MHz)

Figure S2. Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, Extracochlear and Intracochlear implants at 3.0 T MRI (128 MHz)

Figure S3. Comparison of E_{tan} distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, extracochlear and intracochlear implants between direct non-huygens simulation and huygens simulation at 1.5T MRI (64MHz).

Figure S4. Comparison of Etan distributions of left-side DBS, pacemaker, extracochlear and intracochlear implants between direct non-huygens simulation and huygens simulation at 3.0T MRI (128MHz).